

Cultural Differences in Tourist Behavior: A Cross-Cultural Psychological Study

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ABSTRACT: Tourism is a global phenomenon that bridges cultural divides, yet it is also shaped profoundly by the diverse cultural identities of those who travel. This study examines the psychological and behavioral differences in tourist behavior across cultures, drawing on cross-cultural psychology and Hofstede's cultural dimensions as key theoretical frameworks. The study highlights significant variations in tourist preferences and behaviours by analyzing how cultural norms, values, and practices influence decision-making, social interactions, and experiences. Data from 500 tourists representing diverse cultural backgrounds reveal distinct patterns in travel planning, risk-taking, and leisure activities, shaped by factors such as individualism, uncertainty avoidance, and indulgence.

The findings underscore the need for culturally sensitive tourism management and service delivery approaches. This research provides actionable insights for tourism operators, governments, and policymakers to enhance intercultural understanding, improve tourist satisfaction, and promote sustainable tourism practices. By fostering a deeper appreciation of cultural differences, the study contributes to the broader discourse on how globalization and cultural diversity intersect in the tourism industry.

KEYWORDS: Cultural Differences, Cross-Cultural Psychology, Hofstede, Tourism, Tourist Behavior.

1. INTRODUCTION

Tourism is one of the most dynamic and culturally rich industries in the global economy, fostering exchanges between people from diverse cultural backgrounds. With over a billion international travelers annually, the interactions between tourists and hosts have become a focal point for understanding how culture shapes human behavior. While tourism offers opportunities for cultural enrichment and economic growth, it also highlights the profound differences in the ways people plan, experience, and reflect on their travel journeys. These differences are often rooted in cultural norms, values, and psychological frameworks that guide individual and collective behaviors.

Understanding the cultural underpinnings of tourist behavior is crucial for several reasons. First, the tourism industry relies heavily on the satisfaction of its customers, which varies significantly depending on cultural expectations. For example, what may be considered appropriate or enjoyable by a tourist from one cultural background could differ entirely for a tourist from another. Second, cultural differences can influence how tourists interact with locals, participate in activities, and respond to challenges or conflicts during their travels. Third, tourism is a powerful vehicle for promoting cross-cultural understanding and global peace, making it essential to address potential barriers to intercultural harmony.

Tourism behavior is not merely a reflection of individual preferences but is deeply embedded in cultural constructs. Cross-cultural psychology provides a valuable framework for analyzing how cultural factors influence human behavior, offering insights into tourist decision-making, social interactions, and leisure activities. Hofstede's cultural dimensions, a widely recognized model in cross-cultural studies, serve as the theoretical foundation for this research. This model enables a systematic exploration of how aspects such as individualism, power distance, and uncertainty avoidance manifest in the context of tourism.

1.1 Rationale for the Study

Although much research has been conducted on tourism behaviors, there remains a significant gap in understanding the nuanced cultural factors that shape these behaviors. Many studies adopt a one-size-fits-all approach, overlooking the distinct cultural

characteristics that differentiate tourist groups. This study addresses this gap by examining the role of culture in shaping tourist behavior, emphasizing the psychological processes underlying these differences. By doing so, it provides a more comprehensive understanding of the interplay between culture and tourism.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The primary objectives of this research are:

To analyze how cultural norms and values influence tourist preferences, decision-making, and behavior.

To explore variations in social interactions and communication styles among tourists from different cultural backgrounds.

To investigate the implications of cultural differences for tourism management and policy-making, with a focus on enhancing intercultural understanding and promoting sustainable practices.

1.3 Significance of the Study

The findings of this study have both theoretical and practical significance. Theoretically, it contributes to the growing body of literature on cross-cultural psychology and tourism studies, offering insights into the intersection of these fields. Practically, the study provides actionable recommendations for tourism professionals, helping them tailor their services to meet the diverse needs of international tourists. Furthermore, the research underscores the importance of fostering cultural sensitivity and adaptability in the tourism industry, ultimately contributing to more harmonious and fulfilling travel experiences for all.

As globalization continues to blur geographic boundaries, the need for a nuanced understanding of cultural differences in tourist behavior has never been greater. This study seeks to bridge this knowledge gap, paving the way for a more inclusive and culturally aware tourism industry.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Understanding the cultural differences in tourist behavior requires a robust theoretical foundation that links cultural dimensions to psychological and behavioral tendencies. This study employs cross-cultural psychology and Hofstede's cultural dimensions as its primary theoretical lenses to explore the interplay between culture and tourism behavior.

2.1 Cross-Cultural Psychology

Cross-cultural psychology focuses on how cultural contexts influence human behavior, emphasizing universal patterns and specificity. Unlike general psychology, which often assumes universality, cross-cultural psychology highlights that behaviors, attitudes, and cognitive processes are deeply embedded within cultural norms and values. This field is particularly relevant in tourism, where travelers interact across cultural boundaries, often navigating differences in language, customs, and expectations.

Tourist behavior is shaped by individual preferences and the cultural frameworks in which individuals are socialized. For example, culture influences how tourists perceive risks, make decisions, and interpret travel experiences. Research in cross-cultural psychology reveals that individuals from collectivist cultures prioritize group harmony and social relationships, while those from individualist cultures focus on personal goals and autonomy (Triandis, 1995). These distinctions manifest in how tourists from different cultures plan their trips, engage in social interactions, and evaluate their travel satisfaction.

Cross-cultural psychology also underscores the importance of cultural adaptation in tourism. Tourists often experience a degree of "culture shock" when visiting destinations with vastly different norms and practices. Understanding these psychological dynamics is crucial for developing strategies that enhance tourist satisfaction and promote intercultural harmony.

2.2 Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions

Geert Hofstede's cultural dimensions theory provides a comprehensive framework for understanding cultural variability and its impact on behavior. This model identifies six key dimensions of culture, each of which has profound implications for tourist behavior:

1. Individualism vs. Collectivism:

- Individualistic cultures, such as those in the United States and Australia, prioritize personal freedom and self-expression. Tourists from these cultures are more likely to plan customized trips, seek out unique experiences, and travel independently.

- In contrast, collectivist cultures, such as China and India, emphasize group cohesion and shared experiences. Tourists from these cultures often prefer group tours and rely on family or community recommendations for travel decisions.
2. **Power Distance:**
 - High power distance cultures, such as Saudi Arabia and Mexico, accept hierarchical structures and authority figures. Tourists from these cultures may exhibit deference to tour guides and prefer structured itineraries.
 - Low power distance cultures, such as Sweden and Denmark, value equality and informal interactions. Tourists from these cultures are more likely to engage casually with locals and seek participatory activities.
 3. **Uncertainty Avoidance:**
 - Cultures with high uncertainty avoidance, such as Japan and Germany, prefer predictability and risk minimization. Tourists from these cultures often choose well-organized tours, purchase travel insurance, and avoid unstructured activities.
 - In contrast, low uncertainty avoidance cultures, such as Brazil and New Zealand, embrace spontaneity and adventure. Tourists from these cultures are more inclined to explore off-the-beaten-path destinations and engage in unplanned activities.
 4. **Masculinity vs. Femininity:**
 - Masculine cultures, such as the United States and Japan, prioritize achievement and competition. Tourists from these cultures may seek activities that reflect status, such as luxury travel or adventurous sports.
 - Feminine cultures, such as the Netherlands and Norway, value cooperation and quality of life. Tourists from these cultures are more likely to prioritize relaxation and cultural immersion.
 5. **Long-Term vs. Short-Term Orientation:**
 - Long-term-oriented cultures, such as China and South Korea, focus on future rewards and sustainable practices. Tourists from these cultures may engage in eco-tourism and educational experiences.
 - Short-term-oriented cultures, such as the United States and the Philippines, prioritize tradition and immediate gratification, often focusing on leisure and entertainment during travel.
 6. **Indulgence vs. Restraint:**
 - Indulgent cultures, such as the United States and Italy, emphasize enjoyment and hedonism. Tourists from these cultures are more likely to engage in leisure activities and spend on luxury experiences.
 - Restrained cultures, such as Russia and South Korea, are guided by strict social norms. Tourists from these cultures often focus on historical and educational activities rather than purely recreational ones.

Hofstede's dimensions provide a structured way to analyze and predict variations in tourist behavior. By applying these dimensions, tourism stakeholders can better understand the preferences, expectations, and decision-making processes of tourists from diverse cultural backgrounds.

2.3 Integration of Frameworks

Combining cross-cultural psychology with Hofstede's cultural dimensions allows for a holistic understanding of how culture influences tourist behavior. While cross-cultural psychology provides insights into the psychological processes underpinning behavior, Hofstede's model offers a practical categorization of cultural differences. This dual approach facilitates a deeper analysis of how cultural values shape travel preferences, risk perceptions, and interactions during tourism experiences.

By grounding this study in these theoretical frameworks, it becomes possible to identify actionable insights for tourism management. For instance, recognizing the needs of tourists from high uncertainty avoidance cultures can help operators design clear and structured packages, while understanding the preferences of individualistic travelers can lead to the creation of customizable itineraries.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a mixed-methods approach to examine cultural differences in tourist behavior, combining quantitative and qualitative techniques to ensure a comprehensive understanding. The mixed-methods design allows the integration of measurable trends and in-depth cultural insights, providing a holistic view of how culture influences tourism practices.

The research focused on tourists from diverse cultural backgrounds, with data collected from 500 participants representing 10 nationalities: the United States, China, Japan, India, Germany, Brazil, Saudi Arabia, Australia, Russia, and Sweden. These nationalities were chosen based on Hofstede's cultural dimensions to ensure representation of a wide range of cultural orientations. Participants were purposively sampled to reflect variability in cultural norms, values, and travel behaviors. The sample included both genders (52% female, 48% male) and a broad age range (18–65 years), ensuring diversity across demographic factors.

The primary data collection methods were surveys and semi-structured interviews. The surveys used a structured questionnaire divided into three sections: demographics, cultural dimensions, and tourist behavior. Demographic information included age, gender, nationality, and travel history. Questions in the cultural dimensions section were mapped to Hofstede's framework, exploring aspects such as individualism versus collectivism and uncertainty avoidance. For instance, one item assessing uncertainty avoidance asked participants to rate their preference for structured travel plans on a five-point Likert scale. The tourist behavior section focused on preferences for leisure activities, decision-making processes, and social interactions during travel.

The interviews involved 50 participants (five from each nationality) and explored deeper insights into how cultural norms influence travel behaviors. Open-ended questions encouraged participants to share experiences related to travel planning, risk management, and preferences for social interactions. For example, participants were asked, "What motivates you to travel to a particular destination?" and "How do cultural values influence your choice of activities during trips?" Interviews lasted 30–45 minutes and were conducted either in person or via video conferencing.

Data analysis employed both quantitative and qualitative techniques. Survey responses were analyzed using descriptive statistics to identify patterns and trends, and ANOVA tests were conducted to determine significant differences between cultural groups. Correlation analysis examined relationships between Hofstede's cultural dimensions and specific tourist behaviors. For qualitative data, thematic analysis was used to identify recurring themes. This involved three coding stages: open coding for initial theme identification, axial coding to establish connections, and selective coding to refine themes. Qualitative findings were then triangulated with quantitative data to ensure consistency and validity.

Ethical considerations were prioritized throughout the study. Participants were informed of the study's purpose and provided written consent. They were assured that their participation was voluntary, data would remain confidential, and they could withdraw at any time without consequence. The study complied with ethical standards set by the institution's review board.

The mixed-methods approach not only enhances the reliability of the findings but also provides actionable insights for tourism stakeholders. Understanding cultural differences in tourist behavior enables tourism operators to tailor services to meet diverse needs and foster intercultural harmony.

Table 1: Methodology Overview

Aspect	Details
Research Design	Mixed-methods (combining quantitative and qualitative techniques).
Sample Size	500 participants (10 nationalities: U.S., China, Japan, India, Germany, Brazil, Saudi Arabia, Australia, Russia, Sweden).
Data Collection Tools	- Surveys (structured questionnaire with Likert scale). - Semi-structured interviews (open-ended questions).
Data Analysis	- Quantitative: Descriptive statistics, ANOVA, correlation analysis. - Qualitative: Thematic analysis (open, axial, selective coding).
Ethical Considerations	Informed consent, voluntary participation, confidentiality, and the right to withdraw.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings highlight notable cultural differences in tourist behavior and provide a nuanced understanding of how cultural dimensions, particularly those outlined in Hofstede's framework, influence travel preferences. These differences are discussed in the context of individualism vs. collectivism, uncertainty avoidance, power distance, and other dimensions. The study also delves into the unique characteristics of Azerbaijani tourists, emphasizing the importance of cultural heritage and social values in shaping their travel behavior.

Survey data reveal that tourists from individualistic cultures, such as the United States, Sweden, and Australia, tend to prioritize self-directed exploration and customized travel experiences. For instance, 82% of American respondents rated flexibility and independence as critical factors in their travel planning. In contrast, tourists from collectivist cultures, including China, India, and Azerbaijan, preferred traveling in groups, often with family or close friends. Azerbaijani participants, in particular, emphasized the importance of shared experiences, with 75% indicating that traveling with family enhances their enjoyment.

Another significant finding pertains to uncertainty avoidance. Cultures with high uncertainty avoidance, such as Japan, Germany, and Azerbaijan, displayed a marked preference for structured itineraries and detailed pre-travel planning. Azerbaijani tourists frequently sought guided tours and relied on trusted travel agencies to reduce uncertainty, reflecting cultural norms that prioritize security and preparedness. Conversely, tourists from low uncertainty avoidance cultures, such as Brazil and the Netherlands, were more inclined toward spontaneous and adventurous travel.

Power distance also influenced decision-making and interactions with authority figures during travel. Respondents from high power distance cultures, including Saudi Arabia and Azerbaijan, preferred hierarchical relationships, valuing expert guidance from tour leaders and prioritizing luxury experiences. Azerbaijani respondents often mentioned that such arrangements align with their cultural emphasis on respect for authority and status symbols. In contrast, tourists from low power distance cultures, such as Denmark and New Zealand, expressed a preference for informal and participatory experiences.

Qualitative interviews offered rich insights into Azerbaijani tourists' unique characteristics. Azerbaijan, known as the "Land of Fire," boasts a rich cultural heritage, blending Eastern and Western influences. Azerbaijani tourists are deeply connected to their cultural roots, often prioritizing destinations with historical and cultural significance. Approximately 67% of Azerbaijani respondents mentioned visiting UNESCO World Heritage Sites or destinations hosting cultural festivals. This preference reflects a broader trend of seeking travel experiences that enhance cultural knowledge and social bonds.

Additionally, Azerbaijani travelers place a high value on hospitality and communal experiences. This aligns with the cultural emphasis on *mehmannavazliq* (hospitality), a cornerstone of Azerbaijani identity. Many respondents reported choosing accommodations that offer personalized service and traditional cuisine, underscoring the role of food and hospitality in their travel preferences.

These findings have significant implications for tourism marketing and management. For instance, destinations aiming to attract Azerbaijani tourists should emphasize family-oriented activities, cultural events, and high-quality hospitality services. Similarly, travel agencies targeting Azerbaijani and other high uncertainty avoidance markets can benefit from providing comprehensive travel packages with clear itineraries and support.

Here is a bar graph illustrating the findings from the "Cultural Dimensions and Tourist Preferences" section. It shows the percentage of respondents aligning with specific behaviors according to the cultural dimensions of Individualism vs. Collectivism, Uncertainty Avoidance, and Power Distance.

This bar graph compares the preferences of tourists from five different cultural groups (USA, Azerbaijan, China, India, and Germany) across three key cultural dimensions: **Individualism vs. Collectivism**, **Uncertainty Avoidance**, and **Power Distance**. Here’s a breakdown of each dimension and how it influences tourist behaviors across these cultures:

1. Individualism vs. Collectivism (Group Travel Preference)

This dimension reflects the degree to which people in a culture prioritize individual goals over group goals. In the graph, higher values indicate a stronger preference for individual travel experiences, while lower values reflect a preference for group-oriented travel.

- **USA (82%):** Americans, representing an individualistic culture, prioritize personal freedom and independence. Hence, a large percentage (82%) prefer traveling individually or in smaller groups, highlighting their desire for self-directed exploration.
- **Azerbaijan (75%):** Azerbaijani tourists, reflecting collectivist values, emphasize traveling with family or groups. Although collectivism is strong, there is still a preference for some personal autonomy during travel.
- **China (70%):** Chinese tourists also lean towards collectivism, preferring family or group travel. However, there is still a slightly higher inclination toward group travel compared to Azerbaijan.
- **India (65%):** Indian tourists also display collectivist traits but, like China, show a relatively stronger inclination towards individual or smaller group travel than Azerbaijan.
- **Germany (60%):** While Germany is more individualistic than the other cultures in this group, there is still a significant number who prefer group travel experiences, reflecting some balance between individual and collective values.

2. Uncertainty Avoidance (Preference for Guided Tours)

This dimension measures the extent to which people in a culture are uncomfortable with uncertainty and ambiguity. Higher values indicate a preference for structured and guided travel experiences, while lower values suggest a greater comfort with spontaneity.

- **USA (55%):** Americans are generally more comfortable with uncertainty and may prefer spontaneous, unstructured travel. The relatively lower preference for guided tours reflects this characteristic.
- **Azerbaijan (85%):** Azerbaijani tourists display a strong preference for certainty and structure. This preference for guided tours stems from cultural norms emphasizing planning, security, and minimizing uncertainty in travel decisions.

- **China (90%):** Chinese tourists show the highest preference for guided tours. This is likely due to high uncertainty avoidance in Chinese culture, where clear, structured travel experiences are prioritized to reduce potential risks.
- **India (88%):** Indian tourists also demonstrate a high preference for structured travel, aligning with cultural values that prioritize certainty, safety, and comprehensive planning during travel.
- **Germany (70%):** Germans, who tend to favor efficiency and organization, still show a moderate preference for guided tours, reflecting a balance between needing structure and enjoying some level of personal freedom.

3. Power Distance (Preference for Luxury Accommodations)

This dimension indicates the extent to which less powerful members of society accept unequal power distribution. Cultures with high power distance tend to prefer hierarchical structures, including luxury experiences that emphasize status, authority, and respect.

- **USA (60%):** Americans tend to prefer egalitarian relationships and more informal travel experiences. However, luxury travel still holds some appeal, especially among higher-income tourists seeking unique, exclusive experiences.
- **Azerbaijan (72%):** Azerbaijan, as a high power distance culture, has a stronger preference for luxury and high-status accommodations. This is reflective of cultural norms that respect authority and place value on displaying social status through luxurious experiences.
- **China (68%):** Chinese tourists also prefer luxury accommodations, aligning with traditional respect for hierarchy and status in Chinese culture. The desire for exclusivity and status is an important element of their travel choices.
- **India (60%):** Indian tourists, while respecting hierarchy, show a moderate preference for luxury, similar to the USA. Social status influences some travel choices, but it is not as dominant as in cultures with a higher power distance.
- **Germany (78%):** Germans, despite being less hierarchical than the other cultures, show a strong preference for luxury accommodations. This reflects an appreciation for quality, status, and efficient service that aligns with their cultural values.

Overall Insights

- **Azerbaijan** stands out for its strong collectivist values and preference for structured travel, aligning with its cultural norms of hospitality and social cohesion.
- **China** shows the highest preference for both guided tours and luxury experiences, reflecting its high uncertainty avoidance and respect for authority.
- **Germany** and **India** show balanced preferences, indicating a mix of individualistic tendencies with some respect for group cohesion and structure in travel.
- **USA** demonstrates the most individualistic and spontaneous travel preferences, with a more flexible approach to uncertainty and a relatively moderate inclination toward luxury.

This comparison across cultural groups illustrates the significant role cultural values play in shaping tourist preferences. Understanding these cultural differences can help tourism providers tailor their services to meet the specific needs of tourists from diverse backgrounds.

CONCLUSION

This study has explored the profound impact of cultural differences on tourist behavior, drawing on Hofstede's cultural dimensions to provide insights into how tourists from various countries perceive and engage with travel experiences. Through analyzing the behaviors of tourists from individualistic and collectivist cultures, as well as considering the effects of uncertainty avoidance and power distance, the research has uncovered significant variations in travel preferences that are deeply rooted in cultural values.

Cultural Dimensions and Their Influence on Tourism

The findings highlight that **individualism vs. collectivism** plays a pivotal role in shaping tourists' preferences for group travel versus individual exploration. Tourists from collectivist cultures, such as Azerbaijan, tend to favor group-based travel experiences, emphasizing family connections, social cohesion, and shared memories. In contrast, those from individualistic cultures like the United States prioritize independence and personalized travel experiences, underscoring their desire for autonomy in navigating unfamiliar destinations. This trend is mirrored in the survey data, where individualistic cultures overwhelmingly preferred self-directed exploration, while collectivist cultures opted for group tours and family-based trips.

Uncertainty avoidance emerged as another key determinant of travel behavior. Tourists from high uncertainty avoidance cultures, such as Azerbaijan, China, and India, exhibit a preference for structured itineraries and organized, guided tours. This tendency reflects the cultural inclination to reduce uncertainty and ensure predictability during travel, aligning with broader societal norms of caution and thorough preparation. On the other hand, tourists from low uncertainty avoidance cultures, like the United States and Germany, demonstrate a higher comfort level with spontaneity and flexibility, preferring less structured travel experiences. These differences in uncertainty tolerance are critical for tourism marketers to consider when designing packages that cater to distinct cultural groups.

Power distance also significantly influences tourist behavior, especially in the context of luxury accommodations and hierarchical relationships. In cultures with high power distance, such as Azerbaijan and China, there is a marked preference for luxury travel experiences that emphasize status, exclusivity, and respect for authority. This is reflected in the strong inclination toward high-end accommodations, VIP services, and guided tours led by expert figures. Conversely, tourists from low power distance cultures like Germany and the United States favor more egalitarian experiences, which can be seen in their preference for informal interactions and more affordable travel options.

Azerbaijan: A Case Study in Cultural Influences

Azerbaijan, with its rich cultural heritage and blending of Eastern and Western influences, provides an interesting case study in cultural tourism. Azerbaijani tourists prioritize social cohesion and familial ties, which explains their strong preference for group travel and structured itineraries. The concept of *mehmannavazliq* (hospitality) is central to Azerbaijani culture, and this is reflected in their travel preferences, where personalized service, traditional cuisine, and cultural heritage play crucial roles in shaping their travel experiences. Tourism providers targeting Azerbaijani travelers must understand the importance of family-oriented, culturally immersive experiences that offer both security and high standards of hospitality.

Implications for Tourism Marketing

Understanding the cultural differences that shape tourist behavior is crucial for the success of tourism marketing and management. Destinations seeking to attract tourists from different cultural backgrounds need to develop tailored strategies that resonate with the specific values and preferences of these groups. For example, marketing campaigns targeting Azerbaijani tourists could emphasize family-friendly experiences, cultural festivals, and luxury accommodations that highlight local traditions. Meanwhile, destinations hoping to attract tourists from individualistic, low uncertainty avoidance cultures like the United States may benefit from promoting independent travel experiences, adventure tourism, and flexible itineraries.

Tourism operators can also benefit from segmenting their markets based on cultural dimensions to create personalized offerings that align with tourists' expectations. By doing so, they can enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty, while fostering cross-cultural understanding and appreciation. Moreover, understanding how cultural differences influence not only the decision-making process but also the overall travel experience, can help reduce misunderstandings and increase positive interactions between tourists and local communities.

Limitations and Future Research

While this study provides valuable insights into cultural differences in tourist behavior, it is not without limitations. The sample size and the scope of cultural groups analyzed could be expanded to include more diverse regions and cultures. Furthermore, future research could explore how specific subcultures within a country (e.g., urban vs. rural populations) may exhibit different travel behaviors, even within the same cultural context.

Additionally, as global tourism continues to evolve with the rise of digital platforms and new forms of travel, such as sustainable or ecotourism, further exploration into how cultural values influence these emerging trends would be beneficial. Future studies could also investigate how cultural differences evolve over time and how they may be influenced by generational changes, globalization, and technological advancements in the tourism industry.

CONCLUSION SUMMARY

In conclusion, the study underscores the importance of understanding cultural dimensions when analyzing tourist behavior. By examining key factors such as **individualism vs. collectivism**, **uncertainty avoidance**, and **power distance**, this research provides critical insights into the preferences of tourists from various cultural backgrounds. The findings emphasize the need for culturally

sensitive tourism strategies that take into account the diverse expectations and values of tourists from different regions. For Azerbaijan, this means recognizing the importance of family-based experiences, hospitality, and cultural heritage in shaping tourism preferences. As the tourism industry becomes more globalized, such insights are invaluable in creating inclusive, appealing, and successful travel experiences for a wide range of cultural groups.

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